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Performance Analysis of a Burst Transmission Mechanism Using Microsleep Operation for Green IEEE 802.11 WLANs[†]

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Abstract: This paper evaluates the performance of a burst transmission mechanism using microsleep operation to support high energy efficiency in IEEE 802.11 Wireless Local Area Networks (WLANs). This mechanism is an implementation of the IEEE 802.11ac Transmission Opportunity Power Save Mode (TXOP PSM). A device using the TXOP PSM-based mechanism can switch to a low-power sleep state for the time that another device transmits a burst of data frames to a third one. This operation is called microsleep and its feasibility strongly depends on the time and energy consumption that a device incurs in the transitions from and to the sleep state. This paper accounts for the impact of these transitions in the derivation of an analytical model to calculate the energy efficiency of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism under network saturation. Results obtained show that the impact of state transition on the feasibility of microsleep operation can be significant depending on the selected system parameters, although it can be reduced by using burst transmissions. When microsleep operation is feasible, the TXOP PSM-based mechanism can improve the energy efficiency of other legacy mechanisms by up to 424% under high traffic loads.

Keywords: Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN), IEEE 802.11; Wi-Fi, IEEE 802.11ac Transmission Opportunity Power Save Mode (TXOP PSM), burst transmission, microsleep operation, energy efficiency, green communications, performance analysis.

1. Introduction

Currently, the IEEE 802.11 Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) technology, popularly known as Wi-Fi, is one of the primary means for users to connect to the Internet [1]. This has led to the proliferation of smart devices equipped with a Wi-Fi interface, such as smart appliances, wearing devices, and motor vehicles. These Internet of Things (IoT) devices can interact with each other and with other traditional devices, such as laptops, smartphones, and tablets, supporting various data-intensive Internet services (e.g., localization and navigation, online video, video file sharing, and video-conferencing) [2].

25 The huge amount of WLAN traffic generated can cause devices to quickly drain their batteries
26 due to the use of Wi-Fi. In continuous operation, an active Wi-Fi interface can consume more than 70%
27 of the total energy in a smartphone when the screen is off, and still consume 50% when the power save
28 mode is enabled [3–5].

29 The reduction of such high energy consumption has been enabled by the definition of two Wi-Fi
30 certified power save mechanisms that are based on the 802.11 Power Save Mode (PSM) and the 802.11e
31 Automatic Power Save Delivery (APSD) [6]. In PSM and APSD, an 802.11 station (STA) can enter a
32 low-power sleep state when no transmission and reception of data are expected on a shared wireless
33 channel. However, when there is a large amount of data to either transmit or to receive, an STA remains
34 awake for a long period of time, since it needs to wait for its turn to transmit or receive data while
35 other STAs occupy the channel. As a result, an STA wastes energy when it receives data sent to other
36 STAs during waiting periods (i.e. overhearing).

37 Such waiting periods of high energy waste in which data are sent to other STAs can be exploited to
38 allow an STA to enter the sleep state, hence avoiding overhearing. This operation is called microsleep as
39 it enables sleep periods in the order of tens, hundreds, or even thousands of microseconds. Microsleep
40 was introduced in the 802.11n amendment by the Power Save Multi-Poll (PSMP) mechanism [6]. In
41 addition, an extension of the PSMP microsleep was defined in the 802.11ac Transmission Opportunity
42 Power Save Mode (TXOP PSM) [6]. An overview of these and other power save mechanisms including
43 microsleep [7–12] is presented in Section 2.

44 Microsleep has the potential to significantly increase the energy efficiency while maintaining the
45 desired performance. It is particularly suited under high traffic loads and in dense WLANs with a
46 large number of STAs connected to a single Access Point (AP) or to multiple overlapping APs. Such
47 dense WLAN scenarios occur in Smart Homes, High Efficiency WLANs (HEWAs), and the IoT [13]. In
48 addition, microsleep operation can be combined with power save mechanisms designed for low traffic
49 loads [14], such as PSM and APSD, to provide the highest STA energy efficiency across all possible
50 traffic loads.

51 Unfortunately, when existing mechanisms are employed an STA is not able to frequently take
52 advantage of microsleep due to the time delays and energy demands for the transitions to go to sleep
53 and wake up. The duration and power consumption of these transitions depend on the hardware
54 design and can be different for different STAs. For example, the transition time can be some hundreds
55 or few thousands of microseconds and there can be a peak of power consumption in a sleep to awake
56 transition [15–19]. Moreover, microsleep is feasible only if a data transmission has longer duration
57 than the awake and sleep transitions. In addition, the data transmission duration varies with the
58 transmission data length and the Physical (PHY) data transmission rate employed. As the 802.11
59 technology continues to evolve towards higher PHY data transmission rates, data transmission times
60 are reduced, thus making microsleep even more challenging.

61 In order to determine how the aforementioned system parameters can influence the feasibility
62 of microsleep, this paper evaluates the performance of a TXOP PSM-based mechanism using burst
63 transmissions. More specifically, this mechanism allows an STA to send one or various data frames
64 to another STA in a single channel access attempt, while a third one can microsleep during the
65 data exchange. An analytical model to calculate the throughput and energy efficiency of the TXOP
66 PSM-based mechanism under network saturation is presented in this paper. By means of the proposed
67 model and computer-based simulations, the performance of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism is
68 evaluated and compared to those of other power save mechanisms. Results show that the performance
69 of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism strongly depends on the system parameters, since depending on
70 the selected system parameters microsleep may not be feasible. When microsleep operation is feasible,
71 the TXOP PSM-based mechanism can improve the energy efficiency of PSM by up to 424% under high
72 traffic loads.

73 This paper represents an extension of our previous work published in [20], in which a preliminary
74 analysis of the energy efficiency of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism was provided. The differences

75 between this paper and [20] are detailed in Section 2. The remainder of this paper is structured as
76 follows. Section 2 provides a review of related work and a summary of the contributions of the paper.
77 A brief overview of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism is then presented in Section 3. Section 4 includes
78 the derivation of the proposed analytical model for the throughput and energy efficiency of the
79 TXOP PSM-based mechanism under network saturation. In Section 5, a comprehensive performance
80 evaluation of the TXOP PSM-mechanism is provided. Finally, Section 6 draws conclusions and outlines
81 future work.

82 2. Related Work and Contributions

83 An overview of prior work concerning this paper is presented in this section. More specifically,
84 the focus is on 802.11 power management, 802.11-based microsleep mechanisms, and analytical models
85 for 802.11 mechanisms.

86 2.1. 802.11 Power Management

87 Two modes of power management, as well as various power save mechanisms that can be
88 employed in each mode, are defined by the 802.11 Standard. An active mode allows an STA to receive
89 frames at any time, i.e. the STA typically remains in a full-power awake state. In addition, a Power
90 Save (PS) mode enables an STA to enter a low-power doze (or sleep) state for selected periods of time,
91 thus the STA cannot always receive frames.

92 When operating in the PS mode, an STA can enable either the PSM, APSD, or PSMP mechanism,
93 being PSMP the most advanced power save mechanism. This mechanism is an extension of PSM
94 and APSD aimed at reducing the energy consumption of an STA spent in overhearing during awake
95 periods. When PSMP is employed, an STA with buffered data at an AP, as indicated in a received
96 beacon frame from the AP, remains awake waiting to receive a PSMP frame from the AP. The PSMP
97 frame signals the beginning of a PSMP sequence and includes a schedule of transmission and reception
98 times for various STAs within the PSMP sequence. When an STA is identified in a received PSMP
99 frame, it can transmit and receive at scheduled times and sleep at the other times during a PSMP
100 sequence (i.e. microsleep).

101 TXOP PSM adapts the microsleep operation of PSMP to be employed by an STA operating in
102 the active mode, hence saving a significant amount of energy for an STA during overhearing periods.
103 When TXOP PSM is employed, an STA can go to sleep at the beginning of data transmissions to other
104 STAs and wake up at the end of the data transmissions. The decision to sleep is made after an STA
105 identifies in a received frame from an AP that it is not the intended destination. The AP specifies the
106 duration of data transmissions in transmitted frames, thus allowing the STA to determine the time to
107 sleep.

108 In contrast to PSMP, TXOP PSM neither causes an AP to store data frames for an STA in the sleep
109 state nor requires an STA to process the information included in beacon and PSMP frames. This avoids
110 delays of frame transmissions from the AP to an STA, loss of frames at the AP, and the need of the
111 large number of PSMP frames. In addition, TXOP PSM causes no increase in the size of beacon and
112 PSMP frames as a function of the number of STAs, as does PSMP.

113 2.2. 802.11-based Microsleep Mechanisms

114 Various papers [7–12] proposed mechanisms based on the microsleep operation of TXOP PSM to
115 tackle the problem of energy consumption due to overhearing in WLANs. The mechanisms introduced
116 in [7] and [8] allow an STA to switch to a low-power idle state during the transmission of a data frame
117 sent to another STA. In addition, the mechanism in [8] allows an STA to enter the low-power idle
118 state during the execution of the 802.11 backoff procedure employed to get access to the channel. The
119 mechanisms proposed in [9] and [11] specify that an STA can go into the sleep state for the payload
120 duration of a data frame sent to another STA. Using the mechanism defined in [10], an STA can sleep

121 during an exchange of data frames between other STAs. Finally, the mechanism presented in [12]
122 allows an STA to sleep during a burst transmission including various data frames sent to another STA.

123 The feasibility of the mechanisms in [7] and [8] is possible due to the very short transition time
124 required between the low-power idle state and the transmission or the reception state (a few tens of
125 microseconds). This transition time can be considered negligible as compared to the transmission
126 duration of a data frame, and therefore the STAs can take advantage of microsleep. Unfortunately, the
127 great majority of 802.11 interfaces in the market do not support such low-power state dependent on
128 very quick transition times.

129 On the contrary, the low-power sleep state employed in the mechanisms in [9–12] is commonly
130 available in most commercial 802.11 interfaces. The transitions between the awake state (either the
131 transmission, reception, or idle state) and the sleep state can take some hundreds or few thousands of
132 microseconds, as shown by measurements in [15–19]. However, few tens of microseconds for these
133 transitions are assumed in [9] and [11] with no experimental validation. Likewise, no information about
134 the transition time is given in [12]. Only in [10], the time and power consumption of the transitions are
135 based on the aforementioned measurements. Using the measured transition times, the mechanisms
136 introduced in [9], [11], and [12] do not allow an STA to frequently exploit microsleep opportunities; at
137 most an STA can enable microsleep operation for a short period of time.

138 *2.3. Analytical Models for 802.11 Mechanisms*

139 The Distributed Coordination Function (DCF) is the fundamental channel access mechanism
140 defined by the 802.11 Standard. Extensive work has been undertaken to evaluate the performance of
141 this mechanism. More specifically, a two dimensional Markov chain model to compute the throughput
142 of DCF under network saturation was proposed in [21], being the most widely-used analytical model
143 to evaluate the performance of DCF. Refinements of this basic model were then introduced in various
144 papers to account for details of specific operation of DCF, such as finite retransmission attempts [22,23],
145 backoff freezing [24], and other operation details. In addition, some papers analyze the throughput
146 and delay of other DCF extensions, such as DCF with frame bursting [25] and the 802.11e Enhanced
147 Distributed Channel Access (EDCA) with its Transmission Opportunity (TXOP) mechanism [26,27].

148 While the aforementioned papers mainly concentrate on the throughput and delay performance,
149 other papers, such as [28] and [29], analyze the energy consumption of DCF. These papers show that
150 DCF causes high energy consumption in an STA during idle and overhearing periods. In [30], the
151 focus is on PSM as an extension of DCF to save energy, as defined by the 802.11 Standard. More
152 specifically, such paper provides an analytical model to compute the throughput, delay, and power
153 consumption of PSM. In addition, an energy efficiency analysis of a TXOP PSM-based mechanism
154 using burst transmissions is presented in [20]. Results obtained from such analysis show that only
155 when microsleep operation is feasible can the TXOP PSM-based mechanism achieve higher energy
156 efficiency as compared to DCF and PSM under high traffic loads. Such results also show that the
157 feasibility of microsleep operation strongly depends on the system parameters used, such as the
158 transmission data length, the PHY data transmission rate, and the transition time between awake and
159 sleep states.

160 *2.4. Contributions of the Paper*

161 The core contribution of this paper is the analytical evaluation of the throughput and energy
162 efficiency of a burst transmission mechanism using microsleep operation under network saturation
163 conditions. In line with [12] and [20], this mechanism represents a possible implementation of IEEE
164 802.11ac TXOP PSM on the top of 802.11 DCF using burst transmissions [25] (similar to 802.11e EDCA
165 TXOP). Basically, when the TXOP PSM-based mechanism is employed, an STA can send a burst of data
166 frames to another STA, while a third one can microsleep during the data exchange. A more detailed
167 description of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism is provided in the following section.

168 The analytical model proposed in this paper builds on the Markov chain model introduced in [21]
169 and extended in [24] to compute the DCF throughput under saturation conditions. Contrary to the
170 papers [12] and [28–30], this paper considers the requirements of the awake and sleep transitions in the
171 derivation of the proposed model, since these transitions can compromise the feasibility of microsleep
172 operation. As compared to the analysis proposed in [20], the analysis introduced in this paper
173 concentrates on both the throughput and energy efficiency of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism under
174 saturation conditions. In addition, a comprehensive derivation of the energy efficiency depending on
175 the feasibility of microsleep operation is provided in the proposed analysis. Moreover, a comprehensive
176 performance evaluation of the proposed TXOP PSM-based mechanism as a function of various system
177 parameters is illustrated and discussed in this paper, not considered in [20].

178 The proposed analysis allows the determination of the critical system parameters that influence
179 the performance of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism and other microsleep mechanisms such as those
180 in [7–12]. Computer-based simulations are used to validate the proposed analysis. Results presented in
181 this paper contribute to the development of advanced microsleep mechanisms for the next-generation
182 WLANs.

183 3. TXOP PSM-based Mechanism Using Burst Transmissions

184 This section describes the operation of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism in an infrastructure Basic
185 Service Set (BSS) consisting of a finite and fixed number n of STAs associated to an AP. The STAs of the
186 BSS and the AP exchange data with each other using a shared wireless channel. In addition, all the
187 STAs can listen to all the transmissions between the STAs and the AP.

188 In order to transmit data, the AP and the STAs access the channel following contention-based
189 rules according to the 802.11 DCF specification. More specifically, they wait for the channel to be idle
190 during a DCF Interframe Space (DIFS) period, or an Extended Interframe Space (EIFS) period after
191 the end of a collision. The time that follows either a DIFS or an EIFS period is divided into slots. The
192 AP and the STAs are allowed to initiate transmission only at the beginning of each slot time. Before
193 transmitting, they also wait for a backoff time after a period in which the channel is busy, a consecutive
194 transmission, or a failed transmission. The length of this period is initially obtained as a random
195 number of slot times from a Contention Window (CW) of size ranging from a minimum size (CW_{min})
196 to a maximum size (CW_{max}), called backoff counter. When the channel is sensed idle during a slot
197 time, the AP and the STAs decrement their backoff counters by one, and transmit when their backoff
198 counters are equal to zero. Therefore, their actual backoff times can differ depending on the channel
199 occupancy.

200 As soon as the AP or an STA gets access to the channel, it takes the role of the source STA in
201 the current transmission cycle. The STA addressed by the source STA becomes the destination STA
202 and all other STAs behave as listening STAs, neither transmitting nor receiving frames. The source
203 STA can send a burst of α data frames to the destination STA, including the expected transmission
204 duration in the MAC header of the transmitted data frames. Following the successful reception of each
205 data frame, the destination STA responds with a positive Acknowledgment (ACK) frame after a Short
206 Interframe Space (SIFS) period. In addition, the source STA can send a Request to Send (RTS) frame to
207 the destination STA and wait for a Clear to Send (CTS) frame response after a SIFS period, prior to the
208 actual transmission of data. Note that the transmission duration can also be attached to the RTS and
209 CTS frames.

210 When the listening STAs receive a frame addressed to the destination STA, they initiate the
211 virtual carrier sense procedure defined by the DCF specification. More specifically, each listening
212 STA maintains a Network Allocation Vector (NAV) specifying the channel occupancy time. This
213 information is taken from the duration field contained in the MAC header of overheard RTS, CTS, data,
214 and ACK frames. The listening STAs do not attempt to transmit for the time indicated by their NAVs
215 and enable a microsleep operation until the NAV expiration. They can sleep as long as their NAVs
216 are longer than the time they take in the transitions to go to sleep and wake up. If this condition is

Figure 1. Operation example of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism when the RTS/CTS handshake is enabled. First STA₁ and then the AP send a burst of data frames to each other, while other STAs sleep based on the duration carried in the RTS frame. The energy profiles of STA₁, the AP, and other STAs during transmission, reception (or overhearing), idle, and sleep periods are shown in the figure. The notations of time and power consumption included in the figure are used in the analytical model presented in Section 4.

217 fulfilled, the time they can actually sleep is calculated as the time difference between their NAVs and
 218 their transition times between awake and sleep states.

219 Allowing the source STA to send multiple data frames ($\alpha > 1$) to the destination STA can facilitate
 220 microsleep operation due to longer transmission times, as compared to when only one frame
 221 transmission ($\alpha = 1$) is performed. So as to increase the chances for multiple frame transmissions,
 222 the AP and the STAs can aggregate data frames during a certain time before transmission; this period
 223 of time is called holding time. If, prior to expiration of the holding time, they already have α data
 224 frames with the same destination address, they can immediately attempt to transmit these frames.

225 An operation example of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism is shown in Figure 1. STA₁ and the
 226 AP contend for access to the channel to send various data frames to each other. After a DIFS period
 227 and a random backoff time, first STA₁ and then the AP get access to the channel. Either STA₁ or the
 228 AP, i.e. the source STA, initiates an RTS/CTS handshake with the AP or STA₁ respectively, i.e. the
 229 destination STA, and then performs a burst transmission of various data frames. Meanwhile, other
 230 STAs, i.e. the listening STAs, set their NAVs to the duration of the burst transmission taken from the
 231 duration field of the RTS frame and go to sleep. They wake up when their NAVs expire at the end of
 232 the burst transmission.

233 It is worth noting that the operation of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism can also support frame
 234 aggregation and block ACK in a similar way to how the TXOP PSM-based mechanism operates using
 235 burst transmissions.

236 4. Analytical Model

237 This section introduces an analytical model to calculate the throughput and energy efficiency
 238 of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism under network saturation. This analysis builds on the Markov
 239 chain model presented in [21] and its extension [24] to evaluate the throughput of 802.11 DCF under
 240 network saturation.

241 4.1. Assumptions and Notations

242 The network operation considered in the proposed analysis is a fully-connected single-hop
 243 network consisting of an AP and n STAs, as described in the previous section. This network setting
 244 implies that no hidden terminal exists. In addition, it is assumed that the AP and the STAs operate
 245 in saturation conditions, i.e. they always have data frames to be sent. The AP and the STAs employ
 246 the TXOP PSM-based mechanism with the RTS/CTS handshake enabled to contend for access to the

247 channel, and α data frames can be sent in each successful channel access attempt. Data frames of the
 248 same size are assumed. The channel is assumed to be error free and no capture effect is considered.

249 The Markov chain analysis presented in [21] is the basis of the analytical model proposed in this
 250 paper. The reader is assumed to be familiar with such analysis; a brief description of the derivation in
 251 [21] is provided next. In the analysis, ideal channel conditions as well as a finite and fixed number n
 252 of contending STAs in saturation conditions are assumed. The analytical model proposed therein is
 253 enabled by the fact that each single STA sees the events occurring on the channel according to a discrete,
 254 though not uniform, slotted time scale. In such model, the slot time can refer to either a constant value
 255 σ when the channel is sensed idle or a variable time interval when the channel is sensed busy. The key
 256 approximation in the model is that the probability p of collision of a transmitted frame is constant and
 257 independent of how many times the frame has been retransmitted. Based on the conditional collision
 258 probability p , the probability τ of an STA transmitting in a randomly chosen slot time is determined.
 259 Then, by studying the events that can occur within a generic slot time, the throughput of DCF under
 260 network saturation, hereafter referred to as saturation throughput, is obtained as a function of τ . In
 261 [24], the throughput expression in [21] is then refined to properly account for the backoff freezing
 262 operation in the DCF specification.

263 4.2. Throughput

264 The saturation throughput S is defined in [21] as the ratio of the average amount of payload bits
 265 successfully transmitted in a slot time to the average length of a slot time. S can be expressed as [21]
 266 and [24]:

$$S = \frac{P_{tr}P_sE[P]'}{(1-P_{tr})\sigma + P_{tr}P_sT'_s + P_{tr}(1-P_s)T'_c}. \quad (1)$$

267 With probability $P_{tr}=1-(1-\tau)^{n+1}$ there is at least one transmission in a slot time, given n STAs
 268 and the AP contending on the channel. Similarly, with probability $P_s=(n+1)\tau(1-\tau)^n/P_{tr}$ an attempt
 269 to transmit a frame is successful. In addition, $E[P]'=E[P]/1-B_0$ is the average amount of payload
 270 bits transmitted in a successful transmission, where $B_0=1/W$ is the probability that a successfully
 271 transmitting STA can get access to the channel in the first slot time immediately after a DIFS period
 272 and $W=CW_{min}+1$. The probability that a slot time is empty is given by $1-P_{tr}$, and σ is the duration
 273 of an empty slot time. $P_{tr}P_s$, is the probability that a successful transmission occurs in a slot time,
 274 being $T'_s=(T_s/1-B_0)+\sigma$ the average duration of a successful transmission. With probability $P_{tr}(1-P_s)$,
 275 a collision occurs in a slot time, and $T'_c=T_c+\sigma$ is the average duration of a collision.

276 It is worth noting that the throughput expression (1) is obtained without specifying the access
 277 mechanism employed. In order to compute the throughput for a given DCF access mechanism it is
 278 necessary to determine the values of T_s and T_c .

279 T_s represents the duration of a successful transmission. For the TXOP PSM-based mechanism, this
 280 duration includes a DIFS period, an RTS transmission, a CTS transmission, α data transmissions, α ACK
 281 transmissions, $1+2\alpha$ SIFS periods, and $2(1+\alpha)$ propagation delays, as shown in Figure 1. Therefore, T_s
 282 is given by

$$T_s=T_{RTS}+T_{CTS}+\alpha(T_{DATA}+T_{ACK})+T_{DIFS}+(1+2\alpha)T_{SIFS}+2(1+\alpha)\delta, \quad (2)$$

283 where T_{DIFS} and T_{SIFS} are the duration of the DIFS and SIFS periods, respectively, and δ is the
 284 propagation delay. T_{RTS} , T_{CTS} , T_{DATA} , and T_{ACK} are the times required to transmit the RTS, CTS, data,
 285 and ACK frames, respectively. In addition, α is the number of data frames that the source STA is
 286 allowed to transmit to the destination STA in a successful channel access attempt.

287 T_c represents the duration of a collision. Either if DCF or the TXOP PSM-based mechanism is
 288 employed, this duration comprises the RTS transmission plus the propagation delay and an EIFS
 289 period, thus $T_c=T_{RTS}+\delta+T_{EIFS}$.

290 In order to account for burst transmissions, β is defined as the number of data frames transmitted
 291 in a successful channel access attempt. Hence, the numerator in (1) is rewritten as $\beta P_{tr} P_s E[P]'$.
 292 Since each successful channel access attempt using the TXOP PSM-based mechanism includes the
 293 transmission of α data frames, $\beta = \alpha$.

294 4.3. Energy Efficiency

295 The energy efficiency under network saturation η , hereafter referred to as saturation energy
 296 efficiency, is defined herein as the ratio of the average number of payload bits successfully transmitted
 297 in a slot time to the average amount of energy consumed in a slot time. The saturation energy efficiency
 298 is derived following a similar rationale to that used in the derivation of the saturation throughput in
 299 [21] and [24]. Using (1) and the derivation above to compute S , η can be expressed as

$$\eta = \frac{\beta P_{tr} P_s E[P]'}{(1 - P_{tr}) E_\sigma + P_{tr} P_s E'_s + P_{tr} (1 - P_s) E'_c} \quad (3)$$

300 where E_σ is the energy consumed during an empty slot time. In addition, E'_s and E'_c are the
 301 average energy consumed during a successful transmission and a collision, respectively.

302 Since n STAs and the AP consume energy for being idle during an empty slot time σ , E_σ is given
 303 by

$$E_\sigma = \sigma (n+1) \rho_i, \quad (4)$$

304 where ρ_i is the power consumption corresponding to the idle state.

305 Using T'_s , E'_s can be derived as

$$E'_s = \frac{E_s}{1 - B_0} + \sigma (n+1) \rho_i, \quad (5)$$

306 where E_s is given by the sum of various energy consumption components, being E_t , E_r , E_i , E_{sw} ,
 307 and E_{sl} the energy consumed in the transmission, reception, idle, switch, and sleep states, respectively.

308 The expression of E_s depends on whether the listening STAs are able to sleep during a successful
 309 transmission or not. To determine this, the microsleep period during a successful transmission T_{sl} is
 310 computed as the time difference between the total transmission duration available for sleeping and
 311 the transition time between awake and sleep states. More specifically, when the TXOP PSM-based
 312 mechanism is employed this duration comprises all that occurs following the RTS transmission plus
 313 the propagation delay. As shown in Figure 1, this duration includes the CTS transmission, α data
 314 transmissions, α ACK transmissions, $1+2\alpha$ SIFS periods, and $1+2\alpha$ propagation delays. Being $T_{i \rightarrow sl}$ and
 315 $T_{sl \rightarrow i}$ the time required to switch from idle (i.e. awake) to sleep and from sleep to idle, respectively, T_{sl}
 316 is obtained as

$$T_{sl} = T_{CTS} + \alpha (2T_{DATA} + T_{ACK}) + (1+2\alpha) (T_{SIFS} + \delta) - (T_{i \rightarrow sl} + T_{sl \rightarrow i}). \quad (6)$$

317 If T_{sl} is longer than zero ($T_{sl} > 0$), the listening STAs are able to sleep during a successful
 318 transmission. For the TXOP PSM-based mechanism, this scenario is illustrated in Figure 1.

319 Let $E_s^{T_{sl} > 0}$ be the energy consumed by all the STAs and the AP in a successful transmission when
 320 $T_{sl} > 0$. The various energy consumption components of $E_s^{T_{sl} > 0}$ are obtained as follows.

321 In order to derive the transmission energy consumption $E_t^{T_{sl} > 0}$ it is assumed that the source STA
 322 consumes energy to perform the RTS and α data transmissions to the destination STA. In addition, the
 323 destination STA consumes energy to perform the CTS and α ACK transmissions to the source STA.
 324 Being ρ_t the power consumption corresponding to the transmission state, $E_t^{T_{sl} > 0}$ is expressed as

$$E_t^{T_{sl} > 0} = (T_{RTS} + T_{CTS} + \alpha (T_{DATA} + T_{ACK})) \rho_t. \quad (7)$$

325 To compute the reception energy consumption $E_r^{T_{sl}>0}$, it is considered that the source STA
 326 consumes energy to receive the CTS and α ACK transmissions from the destination STA. Then,
 327 the destination STA consumes energy to receive the RTS and α data transmissions from the source STA.
 328 In addition, the rest of STAs (i.e. $n-1$) consume energy to overhear the RTS and CTS transmissions
 329 only, as they can sleep for the remainder of the data transmission. Let s be the number of active STAs,
 330 being $s=1$ (apart from the AP). Being ρ_r the power consumed in the reception state, $E_r^{T_{sl}>0}$ is given by

$$E_r^{T_{sl}>0} = ((T_{RTS} + T_{CTS})n + \alpha(2T_{DATA} + T_{ACK})s)\rho_r. \quad (8)$$

331 To calculate the idle energy consumption $E_i^{T_{sl}>0}$, it is assumed that n STAs and the AP consume
 332 energy to listen to the channel during a DIFS period. Both the source and destination STAs also
 333 consume energy to listen to the channel for the duration of $1+2\alpha$ SIFS periods and $1+2\alpha$ propagation
 334 delays. In addition, the $n-s$ listening STAs consume energy to listen to the channel during the
 335 propagation delay following the RTS transmission. Thus, $E_i^{T_{sl}>0}$ is derived as

$$E_i^{T_{sl}>0} = ((T_{DIFS} + T_{SIFS} + 2\delta)(n+1) + ((1+2\alpha)T_{SIFS} + 3\alpha\delta)(s+1))\rho_i. \quad (9)$$

336 In order to determine the switch energy consumption $E_{sw}^{T_{sl}>0}$, it is considered that the $n-s$ listening
 337 STAs consume energy during the transitions from idle to sleep $T_{i \rightarrow sl}$ and from sleep to idle $T_{sl \rightarrow i}$.
 338 Being $\rho_{sl \rightarrow i}$ and $\rho_{i \rightarrow sl}$ the power consumption for switching from sleep to idle and from idle to sleep,
 339 respectively, $E_{sw}^{T_{sl}>0}$ is computed as

$$E_{sw}^{T_{sl}>0} = (T_{i \rightarrow sl}\rho_{i \rightarrow sl} + T_{sl \rightarrow i}\rho_{sl \rightarrow i})(n-s). \quad (10)$$

340 To derive the sleep energy consumption $E_{sl}^{T_{sl}>0}$, it is assumed that the $n-s$ listening STAs consume
 341 energy to sleep during the microsleep period T_{sl} . Hence, $E_{sl}^{T_{sl}>0}$ is calculated as

$$E_{sl}^{T_{sl}>0} = T_{sl}(n-s)\rho_{sl}, \quad (11)$$

342 where ρ_{sl} is the power consumed in the sleep state.

343 Based on the above, $E_s^{T_{sl}>0}$ can be obtained as

$$E_s^{T_{sl}>0} = E_t^{T_{sl}>0} + E_r^{T_{sl}>0} + E_i^{T_{sl}>0} + E_{sw}^{T_{sl}>0} + E_{sl}^{T_{sl}>0}. \quad (12)$$

344 Otherwise, if T_{sl} is equal to or shorter than zero ($T_{sl} \leq 0$), the listening STAs cannot sleep and
 345 remain awake consuming energy for listening to the whole data exchange. Let $E_s^{T_{sl} \leq 0}$ be the energy
 346 consumed by all the STAs and the AP in a successful transmission when $T_{sl} \leq 0$. The various energy
 347 consumption components of $E_s^{T_{sl} \leq 0}$ for the TXOP PSM-based mechanism are computed as follows.

348 The transmission energy consumption $E_t^{T_{sl} \leq 0}$ is given by (7), since both the source and destination
 349 STAs consume energy to transmit their respective frames.

350 To compute the reception energy consumption $E_r^{T_{sl} \leq 0}$, it is considered that the source STA
 351 consumes energy to receive the CTS and α ACK transmissions from the destination STA. In addition,
 352 the destination STA consumes energy to receive the RTS and α data transmissions from the source STA.
 353 The $n-1$ listening STAs consume energy to overhear the RTS, CTS, α data, and α ACK transmissions.
 354 This yields

$$E_r^{T_{sl} \leq 0} = (T_{RTS} + T_{CTS} + \alpha(T_{DATA} + T_{ACK}))n\rho_r. \quad (13)$$

355 To calculate the idle energy consumption $E_i^{T_{sl} \leq 0}$, it is assumed that n STAs and the AP consume
 356 energy for being idle during a DIFS period, $1+2\alpha$ SIFS periods, and $2(1+\alpha)$ propagation delays
 357 interleaving the transmissions. Thus, $E_i^{T_{sl} \leq 0}$ is expressed as

$$E_i^{T_{sl} \leq 0} = (T_{DIFS} + (1+2\alpha)T_{SIFS} + 2(1+\alpha)\delta)(n+1)\rho_i. \quad (14)$$

358 The listening STAs consume no energy for switching between idle and sleep states and for
359 sleeping, since they remain awake during the whole data transfer.

360 Therefore, $E_s^{T_{sl} \leq 0}$ can be obtained as

$$E_s^{T_{sl} \leq 0} = E_t^{T_{sl} \leq 0} + E_r^{T_{sl} \leq 0} + E_i^{T_{sl} \leq 0}. \quad (15)$$

361 Using T'_c , E'_c can be written as

$$E'_c = E_c + \sigma (n+1) \rho_i, \quad (16)$$

362 where n STAs and the AP consume energy for listening to the channel during an empty slot time
363 σ following the end of a collision.

364 E_c accounts for the energy consumed during a collision. Being $E[k]$ the average number of
365 transmitting STAs involved in a collision, $E[k]$ STAs consume energy to send the RTS frames colliding.
366 Meanwhile, the rest of listening STAs (i.e., $n+1 - E[k]$) consume energy to listen to the collision of the
367 RTS frames. In addition, n STAs and the AP consume energy for listening to the channel during the
368 propagation delay following the RTS transmissions and during an EIFS period after the end of the
369 collision. Hence, E_c is given by

$$E_c = T_{RTS} (E[k] \rho_t + (n+1 - E[k]) \rho_r) + (T_{EIFS} + \delta) (n+1) \rho_i. \quad (17)$$

370 The value of $E[k]$ is obtained by analyzing all the possible cases that two or more STAs up to
371 $n+1$ STAs (including the AP) transmit in a randomly chosen slot time. Let i be the number of STAs
372 involved in a collision and $i \in (2, n+1)$. The probability of i STAs causing a collision is the probability
373 that exactly i STAs access the channel in the same slot time, given that a collision occurs. For each value
374 of i , there is a number of combinations that i STAs out of $n+1$ STAs take part in a collision. Therefore,
375 $E[k]$ is derived as

$$E[k] = \frac{\sum_{i=2}^{n+1} \binom{n+1}{i} \tau^i (1 - \tau)^{n+1-i}}{P_{tr} (1 - P_s)}. \quad (18)$$

376 5. Performance Evaluation

377 The performance of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism, hereafter referred to as TXOP PSM for
378 simplicity, is evaluated in this section. Results were obtained from the analytical model proposed
379 in the previous section and computer-based simulations conducted in an event-driven simulation
380 program written in the Python programming language. Evaluation of various system parameters such
381 as the traffic load, data frame length, PHY data transmission rate, number of STAs, and amount of α
382 data frames sent in a burst transmission is considered. In addition, performance comparison between
383 TXOP PSM and different reference mechanisms is presented.

384 5.1. Reference Mechanisms and Simulation Description

385 This paper considers two main reference mechanisms, namely IEEE 802.11 DCF and PSM, to
386 compare their performance with that of TXOP PSM. Such mechanisms, as well as TXOP PSM, are
387 assumed to enable the RTS/CTS handshake and can operate either with or without burst transmissions,
388 i.e. $\alpha > 1$ or $\alpha = 1$. DCF and PSM with $\alpha = 1$ are considered according to the IEEE 802.11 legacy specification
389 in [6]. DCF with $\alpha > 1$ (similar to 802.11e EDCA TXOP) operates following the definition in [25], which
390 is also used in TXOP PSM. PSM with $\alpha > 1$ (similar to 802.11e APSD) is based on the operation of
391 DCF with $\alpha > 1$ in [25], and is described in more detail below. Finally, TXOP PSM with $\alpha = 1$ accounts
392 for the operation of the mechanisms in [7–9] and [11], whereas TXOP PSM with $\alpha > 1$ operates as the
393 mechanism in [12].

394 A Python simulation program that implements all the operation rules of the aforementioned
 395 mechanisms using the network operation and assumptions described in the previous sections was
 396 developed. The main motivations for using a custom simulator rather than other available network
 397 simulators (e.g., OPNET and ns-3) are the faster execution of the simulations and the fact that advanced
 398 sleep mode operations are not yet implemented in other existing simulators. The simulator used in this
 399 paper supports all required functionalities to validate the proposed model and to assess how selected
 400 system parameters influence the performance of the evaluated mechanisms.

401 More specifically, the simulated network operation considers an AP and n STAs generating data
 402 frames of the same size by following a Poisson process. All the STAs generate data frames addressed
 403 to the AP at an equal rate λ_1 , whereas the rate at which the AP generates data frames is $\lambda_2=n\lambda_1$. The
 404 destination of each data frame sent by the AP is chosen at random among all the STAs with equal
 405 probability $1/n$. This setting provides balanced bidirectional data flows between the AP and each STA
 406 on average. In addition, the AP and the STAs enable a holding time during which they can aggregate
 407 up to α data frames with the same destination address before attempting to transmit. This holding
 408 time allows the creation of more opportunities for multiple data transmissions in each channel access
 409 attempt.

410 The simulated operation of PSM using the holding time and $\alpha>1$ is described as follows. The
 411 AP broadcasts a fixed-size beacon frame at each beacon interval, after waiting for the channel to be
 412 idle during a Point Coordination Function Interframe Space (PIFS) period. All the STAs wake up
 413 to receive the beacon frame and determine if there are buffered data frames for them at the AP. The
 414 beacon frame includes buffer status information only for STAs that have α buffered data frames at the
 415 AP or a buffered data frame with an expired holding time. When an STA has buffered data at the AP, it
 416 transmits a PS-Poll frame to the AP and the AP replies with an ACK frame. The AP then delivers up to
 417 α buffered data frames to an STA, in accordance with the order of received PS-Poll frames, as soon as it
 418 gets access to the channel. In addition, an STA can wake up to transmit data only after the expiration
 419 of the holding time or whenever there are α data frames ready to be transmitted.

420 The simulated time for each simulation experiment was set to 15 seconds and each simulation
 421 experiment was repeated 10 times. The average values of the collected simulation data were employed
 422 to compute the simulation results for each parameter set. In addition, confidence intervals of 95% were
 423 calculated. Since the width of these confidence intervals is at most 2% of the mean values, they are
 424 omitted in the figures for the sake of visualization.

425 5.2. System Parameters

426 The system parameters used to obtain the analytical and simulation results correspond to those
 427 defined by the 802.11 Extended Rate PHY (ERP) specification with the Orthogonal Frequency Division
 428 Multiplexing (OFDM) modulation. This PHY mode can be enabled in either an 802.11b/g interface
 429 or an 802.11n/ac interface enabling a single antenna for communications. Such PHY mode provides
 430 transmission rates and frame transmission times that allow us to clearly show the significant influence
 431 of the awake and sleep transitions on the feasibility of the microsleep operation of TXOP PSM.

432 More specifically, the available transmission rates of this PHY mode are 6, 9, 12, 18, 24, 36, 48,
 433 and 54 Mbps, with their respective Number of Data Bits Per OFDM Symbol (N_{DBPS}) 24, 36, 48, 72, 96,
 434 144, 192, and 216. While any of these transmission rates can be used to transmit RTS, PS-Poll (only
 435 in PSM), and data frames, only the basic rates 6, 12, and 24 Mbps are allowed for the transmission of
 436 CTS and ACK frames. The selection of 6, 12, or 24 Mbps for the CTS and ACK transmissions depends
 437 on whether the RTS, PS-Poll, and data frames are sent at 6 or 9, 12 or 18, or 24, 36, 48, or 54 Mbps,
 438 respectively. In addition, the beacon frames are broadcast at the lowest basic rate of 6 Mbps. The
 439 specification of these basic rate selection rules is provided by the 802.11 Standard [6].

440 The time to transmit each frame type x using the ERP-OFDM PHY mode is computed as

$$T_x = T_{pre} + T_{sig} + T_{sym} \left\lceil \frac{L_{serv} + 8L_x + L_{tail}}{N_{DBPS}} \right\rceil + T_{sigEx}, \quad (19)$$

441 where all the variables and their values are included in Table 1. More specifically, L_x denotes the
 442 Medium Access Control (MAC) frame length. For a MAC data frame, this length comprises the frame
 443 body or MAC Service Data Unit (MSDU) along with a MAC header and a Frame Check Sequence
 444 (FCS). For example, using an MSDU of 1500 bytes and RTS/data and CTS/ACK transmission rates
 445 of 54 and 24 Mbps, respectively, the values of T_{RTS} , T_{CTS} , T_{DATA} , and T_{ACK} are 30, 34, 254, and 34 μs ,
 446 respectively. It is worth noting that the propagation delay following a frame transmission (δ) was
 447 neglected in the performance evaluation of the mechanisms.

Table 1. System Parameters

Parameter	Value
Slot time (σ)	9 μs
SIFS period (T_{SIFS})	10 μs
PIFS period (T_{PIFS})	19 μs
DIFS period (T_{DIFS})	28 μs
EIFS period (T_{EIFS})	88 μs
Beacon interval	100 ms
Minimum CW size (CW_{min})	15
Maximum CW size (CW_{max})	1023
Preamble time (T_{pre})	16 μs
Signal time (T_{sig})	4 μs
OFDM symbol period (T_{sym})	4 μs
Signal extension period (T_{sigEx})	6 μs
Service bits (L_{serv})	16 b
Tail bits (L_{tail})	6 b
Length of a beacon (L_B)	20 B
Length of RTS (L_{RTS})	20 B
Length of PS-Poll ($L_{PS-poll}$)	20 B
Length of CTS (L_{CTS})	14 B
Length of ACK (L_{ACK})	14 B
Length of the MAC header (L_{MAChdr})	30 B
Length of FCS (L_{FCS})	4 B
Transition time from idle to sleep ($T_{i \rightarrow sl}$)	250 μs
Transition time from sleep to idle ($T_{sl \rightarrow i}$)	250 μs
Transmission power consumption (ρ_i)	1.65 W
Reception power consumption (ρ_r)	1.4 W
Idle power consumption (ρ_i)	1.15 W
Sleep power consumption (ρ_{sl})	0.045 W
Idle to sleep transition power consumption ($\rho_{i \rightarrow sl}$)	0.045 W
Sleep to idle transition power consumption ($\rho_{sl \rightarrow i}$)	1.725 W
Holding time	100 ms

448 In addition, other variables presented in Table 1 are calculated as follows. The PIFS period is
 449 obtained by [6] as $T_{PIFS} = T_{SIFS} + \sigma$ and the DIFS period as $T_{DIFS} = T_{SIFS} + 2\sigma$. The EIFS period is computed
 450 by [6] as $T_{EIFS} = T_{DIFS} + T_{SIFS} + T_{ACK}$ (6Mbps). The holding time was set to 100 ms to run simulations
 451 since this duration enables the highest performance for all the evaluated mechanisms with $\alpha > 1$.
 452 The values of power consumption in transmission, reception, idle, and sleep states were obtained
 453 from [15–19]. The time and power consumption of the awake and sleep transitions were considered
 454 according to the results presented in [15–19]: *i*) $T_{i \rightarrow sl}$ is similar to $T_{sl \rightarrow i}$, *ii*) $\rho_{i \rightarrow sl}$ is significantly lower
 455 than ρ_{sl} , and *iii*) $\rho_{sl \rightarrow i}$ is significantly higher than ρ_i . Consequently, as shown in Figure 1 for the energy
 456 consumption of other STAs, it is assumed that: *i*) $T_{i \rightarrow sl}$ is equal to $T_{sl \rightarrow i}$ (the value was obtained from
 457 [15–19]), *ii*) $\rho_{i \rightarrow sl}$ is equal to ρ_{sl} , and *iii*) $\rho_{sl \rightarrow i}$ is modeled as $\gamma \rho_i$, where γ is defined as the coefficient of
 458 power consumption during the transition from sleep to idle and $\gamma > 1$ ($\gamma = 1.5$ was used according to
 459 [15–19]).

460 Unless otherwise specified, an infrastructure BSS consisting of an AP and 20 STAs, a 1500-byte
 461 MSDU length, and PHY control and data transmission rates of 24 and 54 Mbps were considered to
 462 derive the analytical and simulation results.

463 5.3. Results

464 All the figures shown in this section include solid lines referring to the analytical results and
 465 markers related to the simulation results. It is also worth noting that the results of energy efficiency of
 466 the evaluated mechanisms as a function of the traffic load, MSDU length, and PHY data transmission
 467 rate were presented in [20].

468 1) Impact of the Traffic Load

469 The network throughput and energy efficiency of the evaluated mechanisms with $\alpha=1$ and $\alpha=3$
 470 rounds of data transmissions as a function of the total offered traffic load are shown in Figures 2a and
 471 2b, respectively. As it can be seen in Figure 2a, the throughput of the mechanisms linearly increases as
 472 the traffic load increases. Each mechanism achieves a maximum stable value of the throughput when
 473 the network is in saturation. The saturation throughput of the mechanisms using $\alpha=3$ is higher than
 474 that achieved by the mechanisms when $\alpha=1$ is employed. The reason is that the AP and the STAs can
 475 send up to three data frames in each channel access opportunity, hence enabling the reduction of the
 476 overall channel access overhead. In addition, it can be seen that the throughput of DCF and TXOP
 477 PSM is the same across all traffic loads whereas PSM attains lower throughput than DCF and TXOP
 478 PSM under high traffic loads. This is because PSM, in contrast to TXOP PSM, modifies the operation of
 479 the STAs to receive data frames from the AP in order to improve energy efficiency. It is also worth
 480 noting that DCF, PSM, and TXOP PSM with $\alpha=3$ produce a throughput improvement of up to 32%
 481 when compared to those with $\alpha=1$.

Figure 2. Network throughput and energy efficiency of the evaluated mechanisms with $\alpha=1$ and $\alpha=3$ rounds of data transmissions as a function of the traffic load.

482 In Figure 2b, results show the energy efficiency for each mechanism. More specifically, when DCF
 483 is employed, the network energy efficiency has a similar shape to that of the throughput, and under
 484 saturation conditions it increases up to 29% for DCF using $\alpha=3$ as compared to DCF with $\alpha=1$. This is
 485 due to the fact that the energy consumption of the AP and the STAs does not increase significantly
 486 with higher traffic loads, while the increase in the amount of transmitted data frames is significant.

487 As opposed to DCF, the energy efficiency of PSM is the highest under low traffic loads since the
 488 STAs can sleep for a long period of time. The energy efficiency of PSM is significantly reduced under
 489 high traffic loads, close to the energy efficiency value of DCF. This occurs because the majority of the
 490 STAs remain awake most of the time to transmit and receive data. Note that the energy efficiency of
 491 PSM with $\alpha=3$ is reduced more slowly than that of PSM with $\alpha=1$ as the traffic load increases. The

reason is that the STAs do not wake up until there are at least three data frames to transmit or their holding times expire. For this reason, the energy efficiency of PSM using $\alpha=3$, being always above that of PSM using $\alpha=1$, increases a little and then decreases under low to medium traffic loads.

In such range of traffic loads and when $\alpha=3$ is employed, TXOP PSM attains higher energy efficiency than DCF but lower energy efficiency than PSM, as shown in Figure 2b. However, under high traffic loads, TXOP PSM improves the energy efficiency of both DCF and PSM by up to 110%. This occurs because the AP and the STAs normally send two or three data frames together in a single channel access attempt, hence enabling listening STAs to sleep and save energy. It is also worth noting that TXOP PSM with $\alpha=1$ cannot improve the energy efficiency of DCF under high traffic loads. The reason is that, considering the selected system parameters, no STA can sleep during the transmission of a single data frame. This means that the duration of data transmissions are shorter than the transition times of the STAs between awake and sleep states.

Figures 2a and 2b show that the analytical results corresponding to the saturation network throughput and energy efficiency of all the evaluated mechanisms match the simulation results. In addition, this observation can be made for the rest of the figures presented next.

2) Impact of the MSDU Length

The saturation throughput and energy efficiency of the evaluated mechanisms with $\alpha=1$ and $\alpha=3$ as a function of the MSDU length ranging from 50 bytes to 2250 bytes are shown in Figures 3a and 3b, respectively. Since DCF and PSM show similar saturation performance, the saturation throughput and energy efficiency of DCF and those of PSM are shown together with a single line and marker for the sake of visualization. This is also used for TXOP PSM with $\alpha=1$ since TXOP PSM performs the same as DCF, with the exception of the saturation energy efficiency of TXOP PSM when $\alpha=3$ is employed. In what follows, the terms throughput and energy efficiency will be used to refer to the saturation throughput and the saturation energy efficiency, respectively.

Figure 3. Saturation throughput and energy efficiency of the evaluated mechanisms with $\alpha=1$ and $\alpha=3$ rounds of data transmissions as a function of the MSDU length.

As it can be seen in Figure 3a, the throughput of the evaluated mechanisms increases as the MSDU length increases since each transmitted data frame includes more information. As in the throughput as a function of the traffic load, DCF, PSM, and TXOP PSM with $\alpha=3$ outperform these using $\alpha=1$ for all the MSDU lengths. The throughput improvement ranges from 75% to 24% as the MSDU length increases up to 2250 bytes. This reduction of the throughput improvement is caused by the fact that the longer data frames are the more the data transmission time increases during channel access, thus reducing the influence of the lower channel access overhead enabled by using $\alpha=3$. For this reason, the increase in energy efficiency for DCF and PSM using $\alpha=3$ as compared to these with $\alpha=1$ also ranges from 72% to 22% as the MSDU length increases, as shown in Figure 3b.

525 It can also be seen in Figure 3b that TXOP PSM with $\alpha=1$ improves the energy efficiency of DCF
 526 and PSM for all the MSDU lengths. The reason is that the STAs are not able to microsleep during data
 527 transmissions. In addition, TXOP PSM using $\alpha=3$ achieves energy efficiency increasing at the same
 528 rate as that of DCF and PSM until the MSDU length is long enough to enable microsleep operation.
 529 This refers to an MSDU length that provides a non-zero microsleep period (T_{sl}). For TXOP PSM using
 530 $\alpha=3$, this requirement is fulfilled when the MSDU length is above 449 bytes. When the MSDU length
 531 increases from such value to 2250 bytes, the energy efficiency of TXOP PSM using $\alpha=3$ is significantly
 532 higher than that of DCF and PSM with an improvement ranging from 39% to 154%. This is due to
 533 longer microsleep periods as the MSDU length increases, thus allowing the STAs to sleep for a longer
 534 period and save more energy.

535 3) Impact of the PHY Data Transmission Rate

536 Figure 4 shows the saturation energy efficiency of the evaluated mechanisms as a function of the
 537 PHY data transmission rate and the number of STAs. More specifically, Figure 4a focuses on the PHY
 538 data transmission rate ranging from 6 Mbps to 54 Mbps. Results for the energy efficiency of DCF and
 539 PSM are plotted together with a single line and marker. On the contrary, the energy efficiency of TXOP
 540 PSM is shown with a different line and marker since its behavior is significantly different from those of
 541 DCF and PSM. It is also worth noting that the results of the saturation throughput as a function of the
 542 PHY data transmission rate are not shown due to their similarities to those presented for the MSDU
 543 length. A throughput improvement ranging from 7% to 32% for DCF, PSM, and TXOP PSM using $\alpha=3$
 544 as compared to these with $\alpha=1$ is achieved as the PHY data transmission rate increases from 6 Mbps to
 545 54 Mbps.

Figure 4. Saturation energy efficiency of the evaluated mechanisms with $\alpha=1$ and $\alpha=3$ rounds of data transmissions as a function of the PHY data transmission rate and the number of STAs.

546 Figure 4a shows that all the mechanisms attain higher energy efficiency with higher PHY data
 547 transmission rates. This is due to the fact that the time to send a data frame becomes shorter, hence
 548 resulting in higher efficiency of data transmission. In addition, it can be seen that DCF and PSM using
 549 $\alpha=3$ achieve an increase in energy efficiency from 7% to 29% as compared to DCF and PSM with $\alpha=1$
 550 when the PHY data transmission rate increases from 6 Mbps to 54 Mbps.

551 As it can be seen in Figure 4a, TXOP PSM with $\alpha=1$ significantly improves the energy efficiency
 552 of DCF and PSM for PHY data transmission rates lower than 36 Mbps. The highest increase of 235%
 553 in energy efficiency is achieved for the lowest PHY data transmission rate of 6 Mbps. Such increase
 554 in energy efficiency decreases from 235% to 60% for higher PHY data transmission rates up to 24
 555 Mbps. The reason is that the transmission duration is shorter or longer depending on whether the
 556 PHY data transmission rates increases or decreases, respectively. Shorter data transmission times
 557 decrease the time that the STAs can sleep whereas longer transmission times increase the microsleep

558 period. For higher PHY data transmission rates ranging from 36 Mbps to 54 Mbps, TXOP PSM with
559 $\alpha=1$ performs as DCF and PSM. This occurs because these PHY data transmission rates do not produce
560 data transmission times enabling microsleep operation based on the awake and sleep transition times
561 of the STAs.

562 In addition, it can be seen in Figure 4a that TXOP PSM using $\alpha=3$ can allow the STAs to sleep for
563 all the PHY data transmission rates, achieving the highest energy efficiency value. The improvement
564 ranging from 424% to 110% for TXOP PSM when compared to DCF and PSM is obtained when the
565 PHY data transmission rate increases from 6 Mbps to 54 Mbps.

566 4) Impact of the Number of STAs

567 Figure 4b shows the saturation energy efficiency of the evaluated mechanisms with $\alpha=1$ and $\alpha=3$
568 as a function of the number of STAs up to 100 STAs. The energy efficiency of DCF and PSM as well
569 as that of TXOP PSM with $\alpha=1$ are shown by a single line and marker. A different line and marker
570 are used to plot the energy efficiency of TXOP PSM with $\alpha=3$. In addition, in line with the PHY data
571 transmission rate, results for the saturation throughput as a function of the number of STAs are omitted.
572 DCF, PSM, and TXOP PSM using $\alpha=3$ achieve a high stable throughput improvement that ranges from
573 28% to 39% when compared to DCF, PSM, and TXOP PSM with $\alpha=1$ as the number of STAs increases
574 up to 100 STAs.

575 As shown in Figure 4b, the energy efficiency of all the mechanisms decreases as the number of
576 STAs in the network increases. The reason is that more STAs consume energy for overhearing frames
577 sent to the AP or other STAs. More specifically, DCF and PSM with $\alpha=3$ attain an increase in energy
578 efficiency that ranges from 25% to 35% as compared to when they employ $\alpha=1$ with larger numbers of
579 STAs up to 100 STAs. This is due to the reduction of the overall channel access overheard enabled by
580 the use of $\alpha=3$.

581 In addition, it can be seen in Figure 4b that the energy efficiency of TXOP PSM using $\alpha=1$ is the
582 same as that of DCF and PSM. However, TXOP PSM with $\alpha=3$ achieves the highest energy efficiency
583 for numbers of STAs above 1 STA as compared to DCF and PSM. No improvement over DCF and PSM
584 is obtained when the network is composed of the AP and an STA, since this STA can never go to sleep.
585 For larger numbers of STAs from 2 STAs to 100 STAs, TXOP PSM provides a significant increase in
586 energy efficiency between 23% and 122%, since more STAs can sleep and consequently save energy.

587 5) Impact of the Number of α -Rounds of Data Transmissions

588 The saturation throughput and energy efficiency of the evaluated mechanisms as a function of
589 the number of α -rounds of data transmissions from $\alpha=1$ to $\alpha=10$ are presented in Figures 5a and 5b,
590 respectively. As it can be seen in Figure 5a, the throughput of the mechanisms increases as the value
591 of α increases, since more data frames can be sent in each channel access attempt. The maximum
592 throughput is achieved for $\alpha=10$, although the throughput increases slightly after $\alpha=5$. This occurs
593 because the contribution of the reduced channel access overhead to the total transmission time becomes
594 marginal as compared to that of the data transmission time. For this reason, the maximum throughput
595 improvement of DCF, PSM, and TXOP PSM between $\alpha=1$ and $\alpha=10$ is up to 48%. In addition, an
596 increase of up to 44% in energy efficiency for DCF and PSM between $\alpha=1$ and $\alpha=10$ can be seen in
597 Figure 5b.

Figure 5. Saturation throughput and energy efficiency of the evaluated mechanisms as a function the number of α -rounds of data transmissions.

598 As it can also be seen in Figure 5b, the energy efficiency of TXOP PSM significantly increases
 599 between $\alpha=1$ and $\alpha=10$ and as compared to DCF and PSM. The increase of TXOP PSM with $\alpha=10$ when
 600 compared to TXOP PSM using $\alpha=1$ is up to 483%. The energy efficiency of TXOP PSM can also increase
 601 by up to 306% from $\alpha=1$ to $\alpha=10$ when compared to DCF and PSM. The reason for these results is that,
 602 as more data frames can be sent in a single channel access attempt, the STAs can sleep for a longer
 603 period and save more energy.

604 6. Conclusions

605 An analytical model to compute the throughput and energy efficiency of a burst transmission
 606 mechanism using microsleep operation under network saturation was presented in this paper. This
 607 mechanism represents a simple implementation of the IEEE 802.11ac TXOP PSM mechanism on the
 608 top of the fundamental IEEE 802.11 DCF mechanism using burst transmissions. When the TXOP
 609 PSM-based mechanism is employed, a device can send a burst of α data frames to another device while
 610 a third device can microsleep during the data exchange. Such device enabling microsleep operation
 611 spends a given time and consumes power in the transitions to enter and exit a low-power sleep state.
 612 The proposed model takes into account the influence of these transitions, since the requirements of
 613 these transitions can compromise the feasibility of microsleep operation.

614 A comprehensive performance evaluation of the TXOP PSM-based mechanism, called TXOP
 615 PSM for simplicity, was provided using the proposed model and computer-based simulations. The
 616 performance of TXOP PSM was compared to those of DCF and PSM using burst transmissions as a
 617 function of various system parameters. The results presented in this paper show a strong dependence
 618 of TXOP PSM performance on the system parameters. More specifically, TXOP PSM using $\alpha=3$
 619 improves the throughput of TXOP PSM with $\alpha=1$ (no burst transmission) by up to 75% in scenarios
 620 with heavy traffic, small frames, high PHY rates, and many devices. When $\alpha=3$ is employed, TXOP
 621 PSM also enables microsleep operation and increases the energy efficiency of DCF and PSM by up to
 622 424% in scenarios with heavy traffic, large frames, low PHY rates, and many devices. In addition, the
 623 throughput and energy efficiency of TXOP PSM can increase up to 48% and 483%, respectively, as the
 624 value of α increases from $\alpha=1$ to $\alpha=10$.

625 In future work, the authors plan to evaluate the performance of TXOP PSM using frame
 626 aggregation and block acknowledgment in scenarios including different traffic classes and multiple
 627 shared channels. Moreover, the authors aim at testing the mechanism in real-life environments by
 628 using programmable wireless platforms.

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